

Implementing Swept-Tone and Level Distortion-Product and Stimulus-Frequency Otoacoustic Emission Recording Protocols in Rats

Mathieu Petremann^{1,a)}, Valentina Kaden-Volynets², Karolina Charaziak³, Hubert Löwenheim¹, Jonas Dyhrfeld-Johnsen²

¹*Department of Otolaryngology - Head and Neck Surgery, Hearing Research Center, Faculty of Medicine, University of Tübingen, Germany*

²*Acousia Therapeutics, Tübingen, Germany*

³*Caruso Department of Otolaryngology – Head and Neck Surgery, University of Southern California, USA*

^{a)}Corresponding author: mathieu.petremann@uni-tuebingen.de

Abstract. Here we report initial efforts to broaden the toolbox for time-efficient and objective assessment of cochlear function in rats with swept-stimulus linear reflection-type stimulus-frequency otoacoustic emissions (SFOAEs) and non-linear distortion-product otoacoustic emissions (DPOAEs). We first established SFOAE measurements in Wistar rats to complement standard DPOAEs using a conventional discrete-tone suppression paradigm. Then, for fixed level OAEs measured across a range of frequencies, we implemented a “swept-tone” paradigm, testing different frequency sweep rates. To further speed up data collection, the frequency range (~4-40 kHz) was divided into 2 or 3 subranges played simultaneously. The stimulus levels were swept at variable rates with up to three pairs of stimulus frequencies were played simultaneously. Swept-tone SFOAE and DPOAE recordings showed amplitudes similar to discrete-tone with rates up to 2 octave/sec. Whereas DPOAE could be recorded with 3 simultaneous sweeps (< 3 dB difference), SFOAE results from multiple sweeps were not as consistent. Swept-level DPOAE produced results identical to discrete-tone up to a 80 dB/sec rate and allowed simultaneous recording of 3 frequencies without interference.

INTRODUCTION

Outer hair cell (OHC) dysfunction receives increasing attention in age-related hearing loss and speech discrimination [1, 2] and as an early, objective biomarker of subclinical hearing loss and cognitive dysfunction [3] potentially foreshadowing hearing loss contribution to early onset dementia [4, 5]. Rats provide a well-established research model of hearing loss onset and progression in the preclinical setting as well as for testing of novel candidate therapeutics [6, 7]. Furthermore, rats are broadly used for regulatory toxicology and safety studies and potentially also best suited for inner ear specific toxicology studies [8]. Age-related hearing loss progression has previously been reported in standard Wistar [9, 10] and Fisher 344 [11] rats, but the non-invasive characterization of OHC function was limited to stimulus-evoked DPOAEs. Reflection-type SFOAEs that provide information about cochlear tuning [12, 13] may be more sensitive to hearing loss onset [14, 15] and provide a better diagnostic marker when used in combination with DPOAEs [16]. Although SFOAEs have been studied in different common laboratory species such as guinea pigs and chinchillas [17] or mice [18], they have not yet been established for rats.

In this report, we present preliminary work to confirm the feasibility and repeatability of SFOAE measurements in male Wistar rats comparing within-day recordings and between-day recordings at 72 hours interval. Then, for fixed level SFOAEs and DPOAEs measured across ranges of frequencies, we implemented a “swept-tone” paradigm, testing various frequency sweep rates (0.5, 1, 2 octaves/sec) to determine a rate slow enough to avoid intracochlear interaction, but sufficiently fast to implement efficient noise rejection criteria in post processing. To further speed up data

collection, the frequency range (~4-40 kHz) was divided into 2 or 3 subranges played simultaneously. Results of SFOAE and DPOAE single vs. multiple frequency sweep at varying rates were compared to OAEs measured with steady-state discrete tones. We also studied the effects of sweeping the stimulus level, at fixed frequency for measurements of DPOAE input-output functions at six f_2 frequencies. The stimulus levels were swept at variable rates (20-80 dB/sec) and up to three pairs of stimulus frequencies were played simultaneously. Results were compared to DPOAE input-output functions measured with discrete tones.

METHODS

Animals

For the pilot study, six 13-weeks-old male Wistar rats (Charles River, Germany) underwent baseline only, bilateral audiometric characterization. For the repeatability test, two groups of eight 8-weeks-old male Wistar rats (Janvier Labs, France) first underwent unilateral audiometric tests at baseline (day 1), then again after a single oral sham treatment (day 3). For the swept-tone and swept-level OAE paradigm optimisation, recordings were performed on two 13-weeks-old Wistar rats (Janvier Labs). All animals were anesthetized with Fentanyl/Midazolam/Medetomidine 0.005/2.0/0.15 mg/kg and the body temperature was maintained at 37 °C with a non-electrical heating pad and controlled regularly. All measurements were performed within an IAC soundproof cabinet. Animals were housed in the animal facilities of the Test Facility in groups of 4 with care complying with the recommendations of Directive 2010/63/EU. The equipment and animal housing were cleaned at appropriate intervals. The experiments were ethically approved by the Regierungspräsidentium Tübingen (HN 04/22 and HN 02/23G obtained from Veterinary Authorities).

Instrumentation, Signal Processing and Parameters

Control ABRs were recorded at 2/4/8/16/24/32 kHz on a custom setup using a Fireface UFX II sound card (RME Audio, Germany) and a custom MATLAB script, with stimulus level from 90 to 10 dB SPL in 5 dB steps, in closed field configuration. For signal acquisition a model 1700 Differential Amplifier (A-M SYSTEMS, USA) and a CED Power 1401 AD converter with Signal 7.07 software (Cambridge Electronic Design, UK) were used.

For OAEs, stimulus generation and signal acquisition were controlled using a custom MATLAB-based software via a Fireface UFX II and a low noise ER10B+ probe system (Etymotic) with +20 dB gain. The frequency range of either f_2 (DPOAE) or f_{probe} (SFOAE) was 2-16 kHz or 4-32 kHz, measured for 10 points/octave.

Discrete-tone DPOAEs at fixed level were recorded using f_2/f_1 ratio = 1.2, $L_1 = [70 \text{ to } 80]$ dB and $L_2 = L_1 - 10$ dB. For input-output functions, L_1 was increased incrementally from 20 to 80 dB SPL in 10 dB steps, for six different f_2 frequencies matching discrete-tones measured between 4 and 40 kHz with 2 points/octave.

Discrete-tone SFOAE tests were measured using a conventional discrete-tones suppression paradigm, with probe/suppressor set at 65/75 dB SPL, $f_s = f_p - 50$ Hz and, 10 points/octave.

For the swept-tone paradigm, DPOAE (f_2/f_1 ratio = 1.22; $f_2 = 4-40$ kHz) and SFOAE (f_s/f_p ratio = 1.1; $L_p = 40-50$ dB and $L_s = 65$ dB) frequency stimuli were forward swept with rates of 0.5, 1 and 2 octaves/sec in comparison to measurements with 2 points/octave. Swept-tone measurements were then compared to steady-state single tone measurements, and for the optimal sweep rate the frequency range was then divided into 2 or 3 subranges played simultaneously, reducing the recording time by a factor of 2 or 3.

For DPOAE input-output function, the stimulus level was also upward swept from 20 to 80 dB at various rates of 20, 40, 60 and 80 dB/sec for six f_2 frequencies. Then the optimal swept-level rate was used to play up to three frequencies simultaneously and results were compared to DPOAE input-output functions measured with discrete tones.

RESULTS

In a pilot study, we first demonstrated the presence of SFOAEs in 6 normal hearing Wistar rats. Bilateral control measurements between 2 and 16 kHz showed ABR thresholds from 20.0 ± 3.0 dB SPL to 30.8 ± 5.1 dB SPL and DPOAE mean amplitudes from 10.4 ± 4.5 dB SPL to 36.5 ± 1.9 SPL. For SFOAEs, we chose a high level stimulation with a probe of 65 dB. The residual amplitude was estimated using the suppression method [19] with a suppressor tone presented at 75 dB, 50 Hz below the probe frequency. We included only emissions with SNR >6 dB (average SNR across all frequencies = 22.5 dB). SFOAE amplitudes ranged from 4.9 ± 5.6 dB SPL (2.15 kHz) to 23.9 ± 4.1 dB SPL (6.3 kHz) with some individual maximum SFOAE amplitudes up to 30 dB SPL in the 4.4 to 8.4 kHz range.

To further study the robustness and the repeatability of our measurements with extended frequency ranges, we

Figure 1. Discrete-tone SFOAEs (solid lines) and corresponding noise floor level (dashed lines) for maximum individual and group mean values.

performed baseline measurements at day 0 followed by post sham-treatment measurements on day 3 for two series of animals. All animals demonstrated normal hearing on both recording days with ABR thresholds from 17.5 ± 2.7 dB SPL to 23.8 ± 5.2 dB SPL between 8-32 kHz. DPOAEs showed mean amplitudes from 6.1 ± 6.91 dB SPL to 33.6 ± 1.09 SPL between 4-40 kHz comparable to amplitudes obtained in the pilot study at corresponding frequencies. However, some differences observed might be due to an optimization of the calibration method: speaker calibration using nominal probe sensitivity for the pilot study vs in ear calibration using extended frequency transfer function for the follow-on study. Mean SFOAE amplitudes ranged from 6.94 ± 11.21 dB SPL (29.78 kHz) to 32.6 ± 1.89 dB SPL (5.72 kHz) and some individual maximum SFOAE amplitudes were recorded up to 38 and 43 dB SPL in the 4.96-5.6 and 13.5-15.6 kHz range, respectively (Fig.1).

As a starting point for the swept-tone OAE paradigm implementation, swept-tone SFOAE ($f_s/f_s=1.1$, $L_p/L_s= 40/65$ SPL) and DPOAE ($f_2/f_1=1.22$, $L_1/L_2=70-60$ dB SPL) were recorded for 0.5, 1 and 2 octave/sec sweep rates and compared with their corresponding discrete-tone measurement within the frequency range [4-40] kHz for the same animal within the same recording session. Both swept-tone DPOAEs and SFOAEs showed amplitudes similar to discrete-tone recordings with rates up to 2 octave/sec (Fig 2). To give an idea about the measurement speed gain, discrete-tone DPOAE recording for 30 points/oct, 4-40 kHz and 32 averages lasts 15 minutes whereas swept-tone recordings with sweep rate of 1/2000, 1/1000 and 2/1000 oct/ms last respectively 12, 6 and 3 minutes. For SFOAEs, discrete-tone recording with similar setting lasts 14 minutes while swept-tone recording with 64 averages last 14, 7 and 3.5 minutes for respectively 1/2000, 1/1000 and 1/2000 oct/ms.

The intermediate sweep rate of 1 octave/sec was then selected to compare a single frequency sweep to multi frequency sweeps with the 4-40 kHz range divided into 2 or 3 subranges presented simultaneously (Fig.3). The results showed that whereas DPOAEs could be recorded with 3 simultaneous sweeps (< 3 dB difference) for a recording time of 2.5 minutes, SFOAEs from multiple sweeps were not as consistent. These SFOAE results were confirmed by repeating the sweep test on a second animal with higher probe level ($L_p/L_s= 50/65$ dB SPL).

Figure 2. Amplitude (solid lines) of swept (ST) DPOAE (A) and SFOAEs (B) at various sweep rates and their corresponding noise floor level (dashed lines) in comparison to discrete-tone recordings (DT).

Figure 3. Amplitude (solid lines) of swept (ST) DPOAE (A) and SFOAEs (B) for 2 and 3 concurrent sweeps (ncs) and their noise floor level (dashed lines) in comparison to single sweep recording.

DPOAE input-output function recordings have also been optimized using swept-level stimuli for a series of six fixed frequencies (4, 5.8, 8.6, 12.6, 18.5, and 27.2 kHz) matching discrete-tone DPOAE recordings performed separately for $L_1=20$ to 80 dB SPL in 10 dB steps. Level sweep rates of 20, 40, 60 and 80 dB/sec have been tested and compared to discrete tone recordings, Fig. 4AB. All sweep rates produced results identical to discrete-tone recordings up to a 80 dB/sec rate. Recordings of fixed frequency DPOAE input-output function using a sweep rate of 40 dB/sec were then compared to swept-level DPOAE for 2 to 3 “simultaneous frequencies Fig. 4CD”, producing similar results without interference as shown for 8.6 and 27.2 kHz. This allows to record up to 3 simultaneous frequencies input-output function within 3 minutes.

Figure 4. Example of DPOAE input-output function for $f_2=8.6$ kHz. Amplitudes A, and phases B are presented for various level sweep rates. Example of 2 simultaneous level-sweep (ncs= 2) recordings for 8.6 (C) and 27.2 kHz (D) compared to their respective discrete-tone recordings and single frequency level-sweeps.

DISCUSSION

In humans, it has previously been described that OAEs provide complementary information about cochlear functions and dysfunction and that linear reflection (SFOAE) and nonlinear distortion (DPOAE) otoacoustic emissions have different origins and mechanisms in the cochlea providing independent information about hearing. Studies of a joint OAE profile [20] described that SFOAEs and DPOAEs differ significantly in their features across patients from normal hearing to moderate hearing loss, suggesting a promising approach in large groups of subjects with sensory hearing loss of varied etiologies. In the preclinical setting, standard DPOAEs are commonly measured for most of the laboratory species. SFOAEs have previously been characterized for species not commonly accepted for all aspects of translational therapeutic development (mice, guinea pigs, chinchillas), but so far not developed for rats.

These presently reported results confirm that SFOAEs can be reliably measured like DPOAEs, in a consistent and time-efficient manner in Wistar rats with fine structure and levels comparable to other species listed. The optimized recording protocols for both reflection and distortion-type OAEs based on swept-tone and swept-level stimuli considerably increases the speed of data collection, decreases variability and increases the consistency of the measurements. These protocols also give the opportunity to include more extended, defined and complete measurement parameters for both DPOAEs and SFOAEs, with the potential to create a new standard for routine hearing measurements in complement to ABRs.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by Acousia Therapeutics through an ongoing MSA covering ongoing collaborative work on Kv7.4 activators. We thank Dr. Karina Gültig for support in animal management.

REFERENCES

1. Wu et al. 2020. Age-Related Hearing Loss Is Dominated by Damage to Inner Ear Sensory Cells, Not the Cellular Battery That Powers Them. *J Neurosci.* 40(33): 6357–6366.
2. Parker. 2020. Identifying three otopathologies in humans. *Hearing Research* 398. 108079.
3. Medel et al. 2023. Cochlear dysfunction as an early biomarker for cognitive decline in normal hearing and mild hearing loss, *bioRxiv.02.03.527051*.
4. Livingston et al. 2020. Dementia prevention, intervention, and care: 2020 report of the Lancet Commission. *Lancet*; 396: 413–46.
5. Wang et al. 2022. Hearing impairment is associated with cognitive decline, brain atrophy and tau pathology. *EBioMedicine.* 2022 Dec; 86:104336.
6. Escabi, et al. 2019. The rat animal model for noise-induced hearing loss. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* 146, 3692–3709.
7. Holt et al. 2019. The rat as a model for studying noise injury and otoprotection. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* 146, 3681–3691.
8. Alvarado et al. 2014. Wistar rats: a forgotten model of age-related hearing loss *Frontiers in Aging. Frontier in Aging Neuroscience* 2014, 6
9. Petremann et al. 2020. Natural Progression of Age-Related Hearing Loss in Male Wistar Rats. Poster ARO 2020.
10. Balogová et al. 2017. Age-Related Differences in Hearing Function and Cochlear Morphology between Male and Female Fischer 344 Rats. *Front Aging Neurosci.* 2018 Jan 4;9:428.
11. Souter. 1995. Stimulus frequency otoacoustic emissions from guinea pig and human subjects. *Hear Res.* 91(1-2):167-77.

12. Abdala et al. 2022. Characterizing the Relationship Between Reflection and Distortion Otoacoustic Emissions in Normal-Hearing Adults. *J Assoc Res Otolaryngol.* 23(5):647-664.
13. Keefe et al. 2019. High frequency transient-evoked otoacoustic emission measurements using chirp and click stimuli. *Hear Res.* 371:117-139.
14. Blankenship et al. 2018. Optimizing Clinical Interpretation of Distortion Product Otoacoustic Emissions in Infants. *Ear Hear.* 39(6): 1075–1090.
15. Abdala et al. 2018. Reflection- and Distortion-Source Otoacoustic Emissions: Evidence for Increased Irregularity in the Human Cochlea During Aging. *Journal of the Association for Research in Otolaryngology* 19 (5) 493-510
16. Berezina-Green and Guinan 2015. Stimulus frequency otoacoustic emission delays and generating mechanisms in Guinea pigs, chinchillas, and simulations *J Assoc Res Otolaryngol.*16(6):679-94.
17. Cheatham et al. 2011, Using stimulus frequency emissions to characterize cochlear function in mice. *AIP Conf Proc.* 1403:383–388.
18. Brass D, Kemp D. 1993. Suppression of stimulus frequency otoacoustic emissions. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* 93:920–939.
19. Abdala C, Kalluri R. 2017. Towards a joint reflection-distortion otoacoustic emission profile: Results in normal and impaired ears. *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America.* 142, 812–824